

AEROELASTIC TAILORING OF TOW-STEERED COMPOSITE WING BOXES

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ABSTRACT

Multi-disciplinary optimisation, including aeroelastic tailoring, and the intelligent use of advanced materials and manufacturing methods could provide a step change in aircraft efficiency for the future. In this context, the use of tow-steered composites is explored for tailoring the aeroelastic behaviour of a simple wing model. Using a genetic algorithm, first the wing flutter/divergence airspeeds are maximised and then the wing loads due to discrete gusts are minimised. It was found that the use of tow-steered laminates is beneficial compared to the use of straight-fibre laminates both in terms of increasing the flutter/divergence airspeeds (up to 13%) and in terms of reducing the wing root loads due to gusts (up to 24%). Whilst higher order fibre angle variations provide the best results, a linear fibre angle variation can already significantly reduce the correlated wing root loads due to gusts (up to 21%), and to a lesser extent increase the flutter/divergence airspeeds (up to 4%). Tow-steered laminates achieved improved aeroelastic behaviours compared to straight-fibre laminates by allowing the stiffness distributions and the spanwise bend-twist coupling to be optimised.

1 INTRODUCTION

The global demand for air travel is predicted to increase 4-5% per annum over the next 20 years. The challenge for aircraft manufacturers is to meet this demand while reducing aircraft emissions and noise by more than 50% [1]. The intelligent use of advanced materials and manufacturing methods could provide some of the performance improvements required in the future, by allowing the design of lighter and more efficient aircraft structures.

In flight, the aerodynamic loads on an aircraft wing are not only a function of the aircraft's speed, altitude and accelerations, but also of the wing's static deflections under load and of its dynamic behaviour. Aeroelasticity is the discipline studying the interaction of these aerodynamic, stiffness and inertial forces. The wing's aeroelastic behaviour is important in more than one way, as it determines not only the wing loads, and therefore the internal structural stresses and deflections, but also the airspeeds where catastrophic flutter or divergence instabilities may occur.

The aeroelastic tailoring of composite wing structures was first proposed in 1975 by Krone [2]. In the 1980s, it was demonstrated on the X-29 experimental aircraft, where a washout effect (wing up-bend coupled to nose-down twist) was used to increase the divergence speed of the forward-swept wing [3]. Since then, it has been shown that the application of aeroelastic tailoring may lead to significant overall aircraft performance improvements in terms of reduced weight, reduced drag, reduced aerodynamic gust loads and higher flutter/divergence instability airspeeds [4-8], by concurrently optimising the structural and aerodynamic behaviours. This is typically achieved by adjusting the wing stiffness and the coupling between wing bending and torsion deformations, such as to improve the wing static and/or dynamic behaviour in different airflows.

Aerospace composites tend to be homogenised specially orthotropic laminates, with $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ angle unidirectional plies. Using these types of laminates, the stiffness of a wing component such as a wing skin, is a function of the zero-degree ply angle relative to the wing component, as well as the proportion of $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ plies, their stacking sequence and the total laminate thickness. In order to change the stiffness over a component, it is necessary to add or drop plies, which introduces load offsets

and fibre discontinuities leading to stress concentrations that can reduce the strength of a laminate. The rate of ply drops is therefore usually constrained [9] such that stiffness changes can only be very gradual over a part, which may reduce the design space available with traditional laminates in terms of aeroelastic tailoring.

An alternative to the traditional straight-fibre laminates are the so called ‘variable stiffness’ or ‘variable angle tow’ (VAT) laminates, where the fibre angles vary continuously in the plane of the ply. It has been shown that VAT laminates can be used to increase the buckling loads [10-14] or reduce the stress concentrations around structural discontinuities [15,16]. VAT laminates may be manufactured using different tow-steering methods, such as automatic fibre placement (AFP), tailored fibre placement (TFP) and continuous tow sheering (CTS) [17]. Lately, there has also been an interest in understanding the potential benefits of VAT laminates in terms of aeroelastic tailoring [18,19].

In this study, straight-fibre and VAT laminates were optimised on a simple wing model, first to increase the wing flutter/divergence airspeeds and then to reduce the gust loads on the wing. The wing model is briefly described, before the optimisation results are presented and the performance of the straight-fibre and VAT laminates are compared.

2 WING MODEL DESCRIPTION

As a first approximation, the wing was modelled as a chordwise rigid composite plate, built-in at the root as shown in Figure 1. A Rayleigh–Ritz type approach was used with 8 bending and 8 torsion shape functions. The wing dimensions and material properties are listed in Table 1. Only symmetric laminates were considered, which simplified the analysis by avoiding bending-extension coupling effects.

Figure 1: Simple wing model

Property		Value
E_1	[GPa]	98
E_2	[GPa]	7.9
G_{12}	[GPa]	5.6
ν_{12}	-	0.28
Span, S	[mm]	304.8
Chord, C	[mm]	76.2
Density, ρ_0	[kg/m ³]	1520
Ply thickness, τ	[mm]	0.134

Table 1: Composite ply properties and wing dimensions

The fibre angle variations were defined over the span of the plate (1D) and both over the span and chord of the plate (2D), using Lagrange polynomials [14], such that

$$\theta(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} T_{mn} \cdot \prod_{m \neq i} \left(\frac{\xi - \xi_i}{\xi_m - \xi_i} \right) \cdot \prod_{n \neq j} \left(\frac{\eta - \eta_j}{\eta_n - \eta_j} \right) \quad (1)$$

where T_{mn} are the fibre angles defined at $(M * N)$ equally spaced reference points on the plate with coordinates (ξ_m, η_n) and (ξ_i, η_j) and where ξ and η are the normalized coordinates along the span and chord of the wing defined over $[-1, 1]$ as shown in Figure 1.

Lagrange polynomials were used to ensure that the input fibre angles at each reference point were actually enforced on the plies, although there was no direct control on the fibre angle variations between reference points. Lagrange polynomials also ensured that each additional reference point along the span or the chord of the wing increased the order of the fibre angle variation by 1. Other interpolation methods such as B-splines or Bezier-splines, which allow generally less control, may have been preferred if more than 5 reference points had been used, since Lagrange polynomials can result in undesired rapid fluctuations for large numbers of reference points.

For the optimization studies, the EI/GJ/K beam stiffness parameters [20] were extracted to compare the various optimum laminates. These values were calculated from the standard laminate stiffness matrix terms as

$$EI = CD_{11} \quad ; \quad GJ = 4CD_{66} \quad ; \quad K = 2CD_{16} \quad . \quad (2)$$

The aeroelastic modelling approach was the same as that used in Reference [21]. Despite its limitations, the model was found to capture the aeroelastic behaviour of a simple high aspect-ratio wing at low subsonic airspeeds with sufficient accuracy to allow a comparison between the UD/VAT optimized laminates; this was previously verified by comparing the model predictions with Finite Element Model results in Reference [21]. It should be emphasized, that the aim here was not to predict the wing response with high accuracy, but to compare representative behaviours obtained using the same model, where modelling inaccuracies would affect both straight-fibre and VAT laminate wing behaviours in equal measure.

3 OPTIMISATION RESULTS

In the optimisation studies, the mass distribution and the wing shape did not change, such that the aeroelastic behaviour was only a function of the wing's stiffness distribution as determined by the fibre orientations in each ply. Three different laminate optimization parameters were explored. The first parameter was the number of plies that were being optimized in the laminate, either only the 4 outer plies or all 8 plies. This parameter reflects the choice between an ideal full laminate optimization and a practical laminate optimization approach, where only the outer plies are tailored since they have the largest effect on the plate's bending and bend-twist coupling stiffness (second moment of area effect). Using the practical optimization approach, not only are the number of design variables halved, but the inner ply stack could also be designed such as to fulfil other functions (e.g. strength requirements). The second parameter was the order of the fibre angle variation in the optimized plies, from an order of 0 (straight-fibre laminate optimization) to an order of 4 (quartic fibre angle variation). The third parameter was the dimensionality of the fibre angle variation, where a 1D variation corresponds to fibre angles only changing along the span of the wing and a 2D variation corresponds to fibre angles changing both along the span and chord of the plate. For 2D variations, for simplicity, the order of the fibre angle variation was set to be the same along the span and the chord of the wing.

The effect of changing these parameters was evaluated by comparing the results of four different design optimization strategies: (1) optimization of the 4 outer plies only, with 1D fibre angle variations of order 0 to 4; (2) optimization of all 8 plies, with 1D fibre angle variations of order 0 to 4; (3) optimisation of the 4 outer plies only, with 2D fibre angle variations of order 0 to 4; (4) optimization of all 8 plies, by rotating an optimized stack of $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)$ plies in 1D, with fibre angle variations of order 0 to 4. For optimization strategies (1) and (3) an arbitrary (non-optimized) inner ply stack of $[-45^\circ/+45^\circ]$ s was used.

Two optimisation studies were performed: the wing laminates were first optimised to maximise the flutter and divergence airspeeds only, and then to minimise the wing root loads due to vertical (1-cos) gusts at two different airspeeds with a constraint on the minimum flutter/divergence airspeeds. For all optimization studies, the integer GA available in Matlab with random initial sub-populations was used [22]. The optimisation results are summarised in Tables 2 and 3.

Optimisation strategy	Order of the fibre angle variation				
	0	1	2	3	4
(1)	68	71	76	76	76
(2)	71	73	76	76	76
(3)	68	72	76	76	75
(4)	67	71	74	73	74

Table 2: Maximum instability airspeeds (m/s)

Optimisation strategy	Order of the fibre angle variation				
	0	1	2	3	4
(1)	(1)*	0.79	0.79	0.78	0.78
(2)	0.96	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.76
(3)	(1)*	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.78
(4)	0.96	0.90	0.89	0.89	0.88

Table 3: Minimum correlated wing root load (normalised with reference to straight-fibre *baseline) due to discrete (1-cos) gusts at 20m/s and 60m/s

The optimisation results indicate that the use of VAT laminates is beneficial both in terms of increasing the flutter/divergence airspeeds (up to 13%) and in terms of reducing the wing root loads due to gusts (up to 24%). Whilst higher order fibre angle variations provide the best results, it should be noted that a linear fibre angle variation can already significantly reduce the correlated wing root loads due to gusts (up to 21%), and to a lesser extent increase the flutter/divergence airspeeds (up to 4%).

The improved performance of the VAT laminates can be explained by comparing the laminate structural properties and aeroelastic responses, as plotted for four optimised straight-fibre and VAT solutions in Figures 2-5. In these figures, the flexural axis was defined as the locus of flexural centres along the span of the wing at which an applied out-of-plane force causes only bending and no rotation of the section on which the force is applied relative to the wing root [23].

Figures 2 and 3 show the ply fibre angles, mode shapes, beam stiffness parameters and the V_g (mode damping as a function of airspeed) and V_ω (mode frequency as a function of airspeed) graphs for optimal laminates from the first optimisation study. Flutter is a dynamic phenomenon, where certain wing vibration modes extract energy from the airflow, leading to rapidly increasing vibration amplitudes and eventually structural failure. Wing divergence, on the other hand, is a static aeroelastic phenomenon, where the applied aerodynamic forces overcome the restoring elastic forces, leading to a large increase in wing twist and therefore failure. For the optimized straight-fibre laminate, the torsional stiffness (GJ) was approximately two times larger than the bending stiffness (EI). This was beneficial, because it reduced the second bending mode frequency (mode 2) below the first torsional mode frequency (mode 3) and prevented low airspeed flutter due to an interaction of the first bending and first torsion modes. Moreover, since the outer-ply fibre angle was negative, the flexural axis was swept forward towards the leading edge of the wing, which increased the divergence airspeed (washout effect). However, the forward location of the flexural axis also reduced the damping of the first bending mode, which then interacted with the second bending mode and lead to flutter at 68m/s. It should be noted that both bending vibration modes included some torsional deflections due to the bending-torsion coupling of the laminate.

In comparison, the VAT laminate in Figure 3 achieved a high torsional stiffness inboard while maintaining a flexural axis close to the half-chord location. This effectively damped-out the first bending mode at 64m/s, preventing flutter due to interactions with this mode. Outboard, the outer ply fibres swept forward, reducing the local torsional stiffness, which decreased the amount of energy absorbed by the first torsion mode. This occurrence prevented the first torsion mode (mode 3) from becoming unstable and increased the flutter airspeed due to the interaction of modes 2 and 3 to 76m/s.

Figures 4 and 5 show the ply fibre angles, mode shapes, beam stiffness parameters and the discrete gust responses in terms of correlated load functions and shear load distributions for optimal laminates from the second optimisation study. The correlated load functions F_1 and F_2 are the time correlated aggregates of the absolute wing root shear force, bending and torsion moments for 20m/s and 60m/s airspeeds respectively. The $\max(F_1)$ and $\max(F_2)$ peaks were due to combinations of high root shear and bending moment loads. The VAT laminate achieved a larger reduction in these load peaks compared to the straight-fibre laminate by delaying the peak vibration responses relative to the peak applied gust velocity. This was achieved by modifying the mode shapes and frequencies of the vibration modes excited by the discrete gusts.

For these studies, there was no significant difference between optimising only the outer plies and optimising the whole laminate stack. Indeed, this follows from classical laminate theory, where the contribution of each ply to the laminate bending/torsion stiffness increases with the cube of the ply distance from the laminate mid-plane (second moment of area effect). Moreover, since the wing behaves as a beam, there were no significant advantages to using 2D vs. 1D fibre angle variations. Optimisation strategy (4) had the worst overall performance, since rotating a stack of $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)$ plies in 1D did not allow for the variations in bending and torsion stiffness along the span to be decoupled.

Figure 2: Optimum straight-fibre laminate solution from optimization strategy (1) (Ply 1 = outer ply)

Figure 3: Optimum VAT laminate solution from optimization strategy (3) for a fibre angle variation of order 3 (Ply 1 = outer ply)

Figure 4: Optimum straight-fibre laminate solution from optimization strategy (1) for reducing the correlated gust loads (Ply 1 = outer ply)

Figure 5: Optimum VAT laminate solution from optimization strategy (3) for reducing the correlated gust loads with a fibre angle variation of order 3 (Ply 1 = outer ply)

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study investigated the use of tow-steered composite laminates to tailor the aeroelastic behaviour of a simple wing model. It was shown that optimised VAT laminates can increase the instability airspeeds (up to 13%) and reduce the correlated discrete gust loads (up to 24%) compared to optimised straight-fibre laminates. This was achieved by tailoring the VAT laminates' spanwise and chordwise stiffness distributions and the spanwise bend-twist coupling, such as to modify the wing vibration mode shapes, frequencies and aerodynamic damping.

Since the results were compiled for the specific case of the simple rectangular plate wing with 8 plies and a limited number of load cases, they cannot be expected to generalize to more complex or different geometry wings. Instead, the rectangular plate optimization can be seen to constitute a first practical step towards a more realistic wing box model optimization, with more realistic load cases and additional structural, mass and control effectiveness constraints, which will be required in order to determine the benefits of using VAT laminates for aeroelastic tailoring with more accuracy.

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